

TEACHING PHYSICS FOR STUDENTS OF TECHNOLOGICAL FACULTIES

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14257634>

Abstract. *The article considers issues related to the specifics of professional education in technological faculties. Particular attention is paid to teaching physics using modern computer technologies to students of engineering specialties. The article proposes an approach and system for using ready-made high-quality electronic educational resources in physics, mathematics, and computer science lessons in order to develop research skills. The paper highlights the advantages of various types of electronic educational resources and provides specific recommendations for supporting this teaching practice. The authors put forward assertions that electronic educational resources can be effectively used at any stage of the learning process: when explaining new material; primary consolidation of acquired knowledge; repetition and control of knowledge, skills, and abilities.*

Keywords: *informatization of education; computer technology; fundamental nature of training; professional focus of training.*

Introduction

Today it is generally recognized that the traditional understanding of professional engineering education as the acquisition of a certain amount of knowledge based on the teaching of fundamental, general technical and specialized subjects for the training of specialists is clearly insufficient [1]. In order to achieve a new quality of professional technical education in accordance with the Educational Standards, "informatization of education and optimization of teaching methods, deepening of integration and interdisciplinary programs in higher education, their combination with breakthrough computer technologies" will be implemented. Therefore, mastery of modern computer methods of information processing and the ability to apply them in professional activities is one of the mandatory requirements for graduates of technical universities, enshrined in the Educational Standards[1]. Thus, the specificity of the educational process in a technical university consists in the practical focus of the disciplines studied and the active use of computer technologies, while physics is the foundation for disciplines in the technical direction. However, the analysis of curricula and programs in physics for various engineering and technical specialties of higher education institutions and the ascertaining experiment we conducted allowed us to identify contradictions:

➤ between the need to train highly professional specialists in technical universities who have fundamental knowledge of physics and are able to apply modern computer technologies in solving applied problems, and the practical absence of appropriate scientific and methodological support for the educational process;

➤ between the constantly increasing volume of educational material on physics in technical universities and the educational time provided for its study;

Therefore, the goal of our study was to identify the theoretical foundations, construction and practical implementation of a methodological system for teaching physics to students of a technological faculties using modern computer technologies. A hypothesis was put forward: the development and implementation in the educational process of a technical university of a methodological system reflecting the engineering and applied focus of teaching physics using a

set of modern computer technologies in all forms of classes (including classroom time, independent work of students, including when completing coursework in physics) can increase the level of fundamental training of students and form certain types of professional activity adequate to modern conditions of computerization of production.

We propose to teach physics to students of technological faculties at three levels. Since one of the goals of the physics course at a technical university is to create a fundamental theoretical base for a university graduate in the field of technical sciences, the first level, invariant (basic), assumes solving standard problems and includes traditional laboratory work in physics. Specific requirements for the physics course at a technological university should not be implemented to the detriment of the main objectives of this subject as a fundamental one. Despite the importance of interdisciplinary connections, science cannot be turned into a preparatory subject for studying special disciplines. It is unacceptable for those fundamental classical experiments that radically changed the established concepts in physics to disappear. Thus, training at the first level is carried out in accordance with the principle of fundamentality.

Teaching physics to students of a technological faculties also has specific goals: creating a scientific base for studying general technical and special disciplines; forming types of activity adequate to the professional activity of an engineer. Therefore, training at the second level is focused on the application of physical laws and phenomena in professional activity. Throughout the entire period of study at a technical university, students encounter interdisciplinary connections, connections between fundamental, general educational and specialized disciplines. Thus, the construction of the didactic process at the second level should be carried out on the basis of an interdisciplinary approach and the principle of professional orientation of training. For this purpose, all possible methods, forms and means of training should be used. As practice has shown, the use of an interdisciplinary approach and the principle of professional orientation helps students to reveal the relationship between disciplines, their mutual influence. However, the most important direction in the development of engineering education and its transformation into innovative education "is the organic inclusion of students in active creative work, ensuring their mass participation in research work" [3,4]. Therefore, the third level is of a research nature. The tasks and laboratory work of this level should become the basis for projects in which the student does not so much follow standard methods and known methods of solution, as searches for the limits of applicability of certain methods, checking their reliability, validity, and effectiveness. The process of teaching students at this level combines two important principles: the fundamental nature of general scientific training and the direct connection of the educational process with scientific research. At different levels of the educational process, computer technologies occupy different places. They play a key role at the professionally oriented and scientific research levels. The question is how to most effectively apply computer technologies, what software products to use in the educational process. The computer technology market offers a large number of different programs.

Depending on the specialties (technical and technological, economic, information and pedagogical), priority areas in the study of computer technologies are identified. If the content of the computer science course at the humanities faculties is focused mainly on obtaining "computer literacy", i.e. basic knowledge and skills in the field of the most widespread computer technologies, then technical universities provide more in-depth knowledge in the field of hardware and software, computer and telecommunication systems. For engineering specialties, the priority is information activities associated with relatively complex analysis and transformation of numerical and other information with a high level of abstraction. A specific

applied aspect lies in the focus on modeling methods, automation tools for production and design, the use of table and graphic editors and 3D software. General applied training for engineering specialties is based on uniform tasks of fundamental content and professionally oriented tasks relevant to specific specialties. Based on the analysis of the physics course content and the emerging global trends in the software market, we have compiled a table of professional fundamental knowledge and formed thematic groups where the use of computer technology is preferable [3]. Moreover, when teaching physics, it is necessary to move from programming languages to universal mathematical packages (MathCAD, MatLab, Maple, etc.), which automate dimensional calculations and fully embody the principle of the trinity of numerical, analytical and graphical methods for solving problems. The use of programming languages (Pascal, Delphi, C++, etc.) excludes the physical basis of the problem: program variables store only numerical values, and the student must "keep in mind" the corresponding units of measurement. The most complete study of physical phenomena and processes, as well as the solution of problems of the third, scientific research level, is possible as a result of using the so-called visual modeling packages [2]. In visual modeling packages, the student is given the opportunity to describe the modeled system mainly in visual form, for example, graphically representing both the structure of the system and its behavior. This approach allows the student not to worry about the software implementation of the model, which significantly simplifies the modeling process. Thus, graduates of a technical university, when studying a number of disciplines, including physics, should gain diverse experience in using computer technologies, be psychologically prepared to use them in their professional activities.

In order to assess the effectiveness of the methodological system of three-level teaching of physics (using modern computer technologies) to students of technical universities, we organized an experimental work to test the research hypothesis. The pedagogical experiment was conducted at the technological faculties of the University. 5 teachers (3 in physics, 2 in special disciplines of the engineering profile, 3 in computer science) and 600 students took part in the experiment. During the testing of the research hypothesis, a comparison of knowledge and skills in completing the final diagnostic test in physics of second-year students of the experimental and control groups was carried out (Table 1),

Table 1

Completion of tasks in experimental and control groups (average percentage)

Completion of tasks in experimental and control groups (average percentage)										
Groups	Task number									
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7.	8	9	10
Experimental	99	89	87	77	76	91	85	82	99	89
Control	87	86	84	62	59	80	71	67	87	86

As a hypothesis, we put forward the assumption that when implementing a methodological system reflecting the engineering and applied focus of teaching physics using a combination of various modern computer technologies in all forms of classes (including classroom time,

independent work of students, coursework on physics), the level of fundamental training of students did not increase, and the formation of types of professional activity adequate to modern conditions of computerization of production did not occur; with an alternative hypothesis, the proposed methodological system of teaching physics to students of technological faculties using modern computer technologies contributes to an increase in the level of fundamental training of students and the formation of types of professional activity adequate to modern conditions of computerization of production.

Conclusion

At different levels of the educational process, computer technologies occupy different places. They play a key role at the professionally oriented and research levels. The question is how to most effectively apply computer technologies, what software products to use in the educational process. The computer technology market offers a large number of different programs. Depending on the specialties (humanities, technical and technological, economic, information and pedagogical), priority areas in the study of computer technologies are identified,

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